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Peer Tutoring Instructional Strategy And Academic Performance Of Senior Secondary School Students In Chemistry In Delta Central Senatorial District Of Delta State

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of peer tutoring instructional strategy on the academic performance of senior secondary school students in Chemistry in Delta Central Senatorial District of Delta State, Nigeria. The persistent poor performance of students in Chemistry in public examinations has been attributed largely to the continued use of teacher-centered instructional methods, which often limit students' active participation and understanding of abstract chemical concepts. The study adopted a quasi-experimental, non-randomized pretest–posttest control group design. The population comprised all senior secondary school II (SS II) Chemistry students in public secondary schools in the district, from which a sample was selected using multistage sampling techniques. Two groups were used: an experimental group taught using the peer tutoring instructional strategy and a control group taught using the conventional lecture method. Data were collected using a Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT), which was validated by experts and tested for reliability using the Kuder–Richardson Formula 20. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was employed to test the hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that students exposed to peer tutoring performed significantly better in Chemistry than those taught using the conventional method. The results further indicated that peer tutoring enhanced students' understanding, retention, and active engagement in Chemistry lessons. Based on the findings, the study concluded that peer tutoring is an effective instructional strategy for improving students' academic performance in Chemistry. It was therefore recommended that Chemistry teachers should be encouraged and trained to adopt peer tutoring strategies in secondary schools, while curriculum planners and educational stakeholders should integrate learner-centered instructional approaches into Chemistry teaching and learning in Delta State.

Keywords: peer tutoring, instructional strategy, Chemistry lessons

INTRODUCTION

Science is made up of different disciplines; biological and physical sciences are examples of scientific disciplines. Chemistry is indeed a physical science course which plays significant role in understanding chemical properties of matter in daily life of living organisms that cannot be overstated. Chemistry, as a senior secondary school subject in Nigeria, plays a crucial role in technology and science. As a result, the

goal of chemistry is to help both individuals and societies to grow. Chemistry is one of the science subjects offered in senior secondary schools and it is of great importance to the world of science. Chemistry is the subject that studies the nature, interactions, transformation and the energy consequences of matter. Chemistry is a branch of science which makes people to understand the nature, compositions and usefulness of natural things and materials made by human beings (Omiko, 2014). Obodo (2015) defined chemistry as a branch of science that studies the properties of matter in terms of composition, structure, transformation, interaction and energy implications of chemical changes. Ababio (2016) sees chemistry as a branch of pure science which deals with the composition properties and uses of matter. Chemistry is an essential subject for numerous sciences and technically based specialised courses, like medical science, pharmacy, engineering and other sciences (Chikendu et al., 2021). In spite of the relevance of chemistry in the life of the society, the study of chemistry in our secondary schools is challenged with poor academic performance as a result of several factors including lack of interest on the part of students (Obikezie & Abumchukwu, 2021).

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The reoccurring poor performance rate of students at external examinations like NECO and WAEC in chemistry has been adduced to various reasons such as poor funding, inadequate instructional facilities, teachers' incompetence/lack of commitment and inadequate instructional strategies. While peer instructional strategies have shown promise in various educational settings, their effectiveness in improving senior secondary school students' academic performance in chemistry remains unclear. Despite the potential benefits of incorporating peer tutoring instruction, such as increased student engagement, active participation, and collaborative learning, there is a lack of comprehensive research examining its effects specifically within the context of senior secondary school chemistry classrooms.

Meanwhile, Nnamdi (2014) reported that students' poor performance in chemistry in West African Secondary School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) was as a result of some difficult concepts in chemistry. Some of these concept perceived to be difficult in chemistry are Electrochemistry, Periodic Table, Ionic Equilibrium, Rate of Chemical Reactions, Chemical Bonding, Mole Concept and Thermodynamics. Similarly, according to Chikendu et al. (2021) factors responsible for students' poor academic performance in chemistry include – ineffectiveness in teaching process, poor laboratory facilities and inadequate number of learning facilities in schools as against the consistent increase in the number of students. Other reasons adduced for poor academic performance in chemistry include abstract nature of chemistry, student and teacher factors, difficulty of some chemistry concepts and teaching of chemistry without instructional materials (Nnoli, 2014). There have been a decline in the academic performance of students in chemistry in public examinations conducted by the West African examination council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO) across the country over the years (Samuel and Obikezie, 2020). This is evidently shown in WAEC Chief Examiners' report. For instance, WAEC Chief Examiners' report (2018) pointed out that chemistry students' had poor knowledge of acids, bases and acid-base reactions and were unable to report results of acid-base titration experiments, as well as unable to make calculations on molar and mass concentration. Chief Examiners have reported persistent candidates' weakness in chemical bonding which the failure rate was attributed to the use of teaching techniques as reported by Ghulam, et al (2018).

Salami (2018), noted that academic performance is frequently defined in terms of examination performance. It refers to what skills the student has learned as is usually measured through assessment like standardized test, performance assessments and portfolio assessment. Coleman (2011) asserted that

student's academic performance is the main focus in the overall educational performance. It is referred to as educational outcome. Academic performance is a yardstick used to determine how far a student has mastered a course of study within a given period of time. It is a veritable tool that can be used to determine and predict the standard of any educational system in Nigeria in terms of its efficiency and effectiveness. It portrays the quality of education offered in Nigeria.

Peers are people who share a common or similar status or ability. In the classroom setting, a student's peers are other members of the class. Peer instructional strategy is a strategy in which students support other students in the learning process while the act of initial instruction in any skill or topic should be done by the teacher, students can be successful in providing support, reinforcement or modelling for a variety of academic topics. This form of strategy can involve functional, behavioural or social skills. Peer-tutoring as a pedagogical practice can reduce stress on teachers who are expected to teach large groups of multi-age and diverse student learners (Wolfe, 2018).

Nawaz and Reman (2017) specifically cited peer-tutoring as a "teaching strategy in which the class is organized in pairs of two students that may be of different abilities to act as tutor and tutee in the learning process in order to get maximum benefits from each other" Wolfe (2018) opined that an important facet of peer tutoring is that the student-instructor power dynamic is not present. They also work hard not to just give away answers but to help students discover the solutions themselves (Wolfe, 2018). Instructional strategies are the focal point of learning since these direct the ways in which students learn and achieve their objectives.

From the foregoing, the researcher is interested in finding out how peer tutoring instructional strategy would influence students' attitude towards social studies. Also, the study intends to ascertain whether peer tutoring instructional strategy could influence students' academic performance in chemistry in senior secondary schools in Delta central senatorial district of Delta State.

Statement of problem

Chemistry education plays a pivotal role in equipping students with the necessary knowledge and skills to excel in scientific disciplines. However, the traditional discussion instructional approach often fails to engage students actively and promote a deep understanding of the subject matter. To address this issue, educators have sought alternative teaching methods, such as peer instructional strategies, to enhance students' academic performance in chemistry.

While peer instructional strategies have shown promise in various educational settings, their effectiveness in improving senior secondary school students' academic performance in chemistry remains unclear. Despite the potential benefits of incorporating peer instruction, such as increased student engagement, active participation, and collaborative learning, there is a lack of comprehensive research examining its impact specifically within the context of senior secondary school chemistry classrooms.

It is against this backdrop that this research decided to investigate the peer instructional strategy and senior secondary school students' academic performance in chemistry. By assessing the impact of peer instruction on students' conceptual understanding, problem-solving skills, and overall academic performance, this study seeks to contribute to the existing literature on effective teaching methodologies in the chemistry domain.

Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study is to determine how peer instructional strategy impacts senior secondary school students' academic performance in chemistry in Delta Central Senatorial District of Delta State. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

1. investigate how the academic performance mean scores of students taught chemistry with peer instructional strategy differ from those taught using discussion method.
2. examine how the academic performance mean scores of Urban and Rural Students taught Chemistry using peer instructional strategy differ from those taught using discussion method.
3. determine how the academic performance mean scores of male and female students taught chemistry differ from those taught using peer instructional strategy and those taught by the use of discussion method.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the academic performance mean scores of students taught chemistry by the use of peer instructional strategy and those taught with discussion method?
2. What is the difference between the academic performance mean scores of Urban and Rural Students taught Chemistry using peer instructional strategy and those taught by using discussion method?
3. What are the academic performance mean scores of male and female students taught chemistry by the use of peer instructional strategy and those taught by using discussion method?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and will be tested at 0.05 level of significance ($P < .05$)

- H0₁:** There is no significant difference between the academic performance mean scores of students taught chemistry by the use of peer-instructional strategy and those taught by the use of discussion method.
- H0₂:** There is no significant difference in the academic performance mean scores of Urban and Rural Students taught Chemistry using peer instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method
- H0₃:** There is no significant difference in the academic performance mean scores of male and female students taught chemistry by the use of peer instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Framework The educational theories upon which this work is anchored are discussed in this section. The theories of interest are the Social learning theory and Jean Piaget's Cognitive Theory, etc.

Social Learning Theory by Bandura (1977)

Social learning theory can be called modelling or observational learning or vicarious conditioning. Social learning theory simply means learning by observing others. Propounded by Albert Bandura, a Stanford University psychologist in 1977 who stressed that human beings can learn new behaviour without evidence of reward or reinforcement and even without the chance to practice. All that is needed to be done in order to acquire the new behaviour is to observe or imitate others in real life or film situation. In 1980, Bandura officially called this theory Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) (Nwafor, 2021).

Albert Bandura's theory tends to focus on learning that takes place in a social setting. It holds that individuals learn from one another by watching and trying to emulate one another's behaviour, skills or abilities. To improve students' learning, the classroom, as part of the social order of the school social system, implements student interaction and participation in the teaching learning process. This environment adheres to Albert Bandura's social learning theory (1977). The social learning theory is made up of three basic principles which include: Motivation, attention and retention. The concept of motivation implies those students need to be motivated in order to participate in an activity. This could stem from observing someone been rewarded. Attention implies that learning cannot take place unless students' concentrates on a specific activity.

Conceptual Review

Chemistry Peer-Instructional Techniques

Peer instructional strategy refers to a teaching method that involves students actively engaging with their peers in the learning process (Agommuoh (2019). It encourages students to collaborate, discuss, and explain concepts to one another, fostering a deeper understanding of the subject matter. This approach empowers students to take ownership of their learning and promotes critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and knowledge retention. Engaging students in the learning process has always been a challenge for teachers. With the students' increased access to technology such as computers, gadgets, and the Internet, many teachers have recognized the potential of these tools in facilitating their classes (Ifenthaler

et al., 2018). Peer instruction, developed by Eric Mazur in Harvard University, is an active learning activity which centers on collaborative work (Chou and Lin, 2015). The discussion is initiated with a question which requires application of previously acquired knowledge on a principle in specific course content. During peer instruction, the teacher monitors and corrects any misconception or issues. With the structure of peer instruction, students acquire more problem-solving skills than what they can develop alone (Morice et al., 2015).

One may not cater for all the identified concepts at a go made us resolved at the top-most five, in this study. Other pertinent reasons include that the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) and National Examinations Council (NECO) always parade these concepts. Records have it that in the last 10 years, these concepts particularly numbers two to five have not failed to feature in the students' regional final examination (see WAEC Chief Examiner's report, West African Examinations Council, 2017, 2018; 2019; 2020). (Omoniyi & Torru, 2019); volumetric analysis/titration (Tiimub, Kwara, Tiimob & Jackline, 2021) and chemical equation and equilibrium (Dansu, 2022). The above views may differ from one person to another, depending on the learning environment. Taking organic chemistry as difficult to learn for students depends on its nature, like the three dimensions of thinking and the specific vocabulary to be used (Tenaw, 2015). The nature of chemistry concepts and the technique of their representation (macroscopic, microscopic) conflict with the nature of science regarding their methods of teaching; what is taken by organic chemists for approval in their particular problem-solving is not similar to how students answer questions (there are no algorithms for solving problems in organic chemistry); but problem-solving depends more frequently on the mediating trends in reactivity, developing mechanisms to analyse chemical calculations (Graulich, 2015). One major cause of students' indifference towards chemistry is the non-connectivity between chemistry and one's personal life. Some students are incapable of associating chemical concepts with everyday life; and when teachers introduce topics, the students then ask about the importance thereof in their lives (Hanson, 2017).

By incorporating peer instructional strategies into the classroom, students can benefit from multiple perspectives and insights. The process of explaining concepts to their peers requires students to organize their thoughts, articulate ideas, and solidify their understanding. This enhances their cognitive abilities and helps them internalize information more effectively. A study by Achimugu and Obaka (2019) discovered that students under the leadership of democratic principals' perform better than their colleagues under authoritative and laissez-faire principals; a discovery which accords with that of Paul and Toyin (2017) that the most influential leadership style on the performance of students is democratic. Moreover, Ahosani et al., 2017 reported that students' achievements are influenced by the way school leaders focus on the core business of teaching and learning, and how they inspire the school community, which is the same as that which Karadag (2020) reported.

Types/Components of Peer Tutoring Strategy

In line with the above assertions Nurhidayat et al., (2021), outlined key components of the Peer instructional strategy to include the following:

Peer Review: This gives students the opportunity to evaluate and provide feedback to classmates who are working on the same assignment. For best results, should have clear guidelines for what they are expected to do and a set of questions and focused tasks to work from. A rubric of criteria to evaluate, with brief descriptions of what beginning moderate, or high accomplishment of that criteria would look like is one useful way to provide guidance. Encouragement is also important because students often feel they are not qualified to evaluate other students' work, but peers understand the process of attempting the assignment best of all, and can provide quality feedback.

Collaborative Assignment: Collaborative assignments involve students working in pairs or small groups to discuss course concepts, or find solutions to problems. This is often very helpful in discussion or case-based courses, when students can help each other apply concepts they have just learned. This kind of activity is especially useful if time is included for the groups to teach out or explain their conclusions to the rest of the class, reinforcing their own understanding.

Think-Pair-Share: This type of activity first asks students to consider a question on their own and then provides an opportunity for student to discuss it in pairs and finally together as a whole class. The success

of these activities depends on the nature of the questions posed. This activity works ideally with question that encourage deeper thinking, problem-solving, ad/or critical analysis. The group discussions are critical as they allow students to articulate their thought process. For example, students are asked to quietly think about the best learning experience they ever had. Then students are asked to pair and discuss their ideas with another student. Finally, pairs share a few highlights from their discussion and the instructor guides the whole class to look for patterns in what made for the best learning.

Socratic Seminar: The Socratic seminar is an open discussion based on an assigned reading. The group leader asks open-ended questions of the group and students are expected to listen closely, share their ideas and address questions to other students in the class. This activity work best when the instructor makes it clear to the students that no one person is supposed to have the whole answer- rather each student is supposed to contribute a possible step toward the answer and the questioning process is intended to make clear the next step after that.

Jigsaw: A topic, chapter or reading is broken into smaller pieces and each piece assigned to a different group. Each group work to become “expert” on their assigned piece, reading in depth and perhaps doing additional research. The students are then remixed so each group includes one student from each of the previous groups. Next, each “expert” teaches their piece to the rest of the puzzle is put back together, every team member will have learned something about each piece.

Panel Presentations: A small group of students are given time to prepare an argument for a selected topic. The group then publicly (in front of class) discusses different perspectives on the same topic and may also answer questions from a moderator. This allows other students to think through the various sides of an argument and challenge their assumptions.

Concept of Academic Performance

Various meanings have been ascribed to academic performance by different people. For instance, Young, Reynolds and Wellberg (2010) have defined it as the measure of progress which students make as a result of instruction or training. Also, Denga (2016) presented academic performance as an indication of a student’s performance in a learning task in the school system. To Egbule (2002) it is an indication of the amount of learning that has taken place within a given period of time. In effect, academic performance is a measure of the amount or extent to which a learner successfully accomplishes a task such as reaching set goals for a learning experience (Umudhe, 2003).

Table 1: Format for Grading Students’ Performance Scores

Letter Grade	Score Range	Literal Interpretation
A ₁	80 – 100	Distinction
B ₂	70 – 79	Very Good
B ₃	65 – 69	Good
C ₄	60 – 64	Credit
C ₅	55 – 59	Above Average
C ₆	50 – 54	Average/Very Fair
D ₇	45 – 49	Below Average/Fair
E ₈	40 – 44	Hardly Fair
F ₉	0 – 39	Poor

Empirical Review

The students taught chemistry with peer instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method

A research carried out by Azeez et al (2021) on the effect of Jigsaw and Peer–tutoring instructional strategies on students’ achievement and interest in periodic table of elements. The research design used for this study was quasi-experimental design of non-equivalent group involving pre-test and post-test. The target population of the study was 2, 996 (1210 males and 1786 females) Senior Secondary Schools II chemistry students for 2021/2022 academic session in all 57 secondary schools in Ankpa LGA of Kogi State. A sample of 129 (59 males and 70 females) SS II students from two secondary schools purposively

sampled in the study area. Four research questions and four hypotheses guided the study. Periodic Table of Elements Achievement Test (PTEAT) and Periodic Table of Elements Interest Scale (PTEIS) were instruments used for data collection. The instruments were validated by experts and pilot tested. A reliability coefficient of 0.92 was obtained for PTEAT using Kuder-Richardsons K-21 and 0.89 for PTEIS using Cronbach Alpha implying that the instruments were reliable for the study. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the research hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

METHODOLOGY

This section will focus on the design of the study, population, sample and sampling technique, instrument, validity /reliability, procedure for data collection and data analysis.

Research Design

The study will adopt the quasi-experimental design. This aims to determine how peer instructional strategies impact senior secondary school students' academic performance in chemistry. Nwankwo (2016) defined quasi-experimental design as a study in which some threats to validity cannot be properly controlled due to unavoidable situations associated with the study when humans are used for experimental study. In the quasi-experimental research, the randomized complete block pre-test- post-test design will be adopted. As quasi experimental research, three groups of SS II students each, precisely two experimental and one control group required to write a performance test before and after exposure of the experimental groups to two respective levels of treatments. Experimental group one (E₁) will be exposed to treatment one, T₁ (teaching chemistry using peer instructional strategies). Experimental group two (E₂) will be exposed to treatment two, T₂ (teaching chemistry using conventional lecture method). However, the control groups will not be exposed to any of the respective treatments. Hence, the quasi experimental design known as randomize complete block pre-test post-test design is presented below:

Group	Pre-test	Treatment	Post –test
E ₁	O ₁	X ₁	O ₂
E ₂	O ₁	X ₂	O ₂
C	O ₁	-	O ₂

E₁ = Experimental group 1 (teaching chemistry using peer instructional strategies)
 E₂ = Experimental group 2 (teaching chemistry using discussion method)
 C = Control Group
 O₁ =Pre-test administered to all groups before application of treatments
 O₂ =Post-test administered to all groups after the application of treatments
 X₁ = application of treatment 1 (chemistry using peer instructional strategies)
 X₂ = application of treatment 2 (teaching chemistry using conventional discussion method)

Area of Study

Delta State is a state in the South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria. Named after the Niger Delta, a large part of the state was formed from the former Bendel State on August 27, 1991. The State is bordered on the north by Edo State, the east by Anambra and Rivers States, and the south by Bayelsa State across the Niger River for 17 km and the Forçados River for 198 km, while to the west is the Bight of Benin which covers about 160 kilometres of the state's coastline. The state is divided into three senatorial zones, namely: Delta Central, Delta North and Delta South Senatorial District.

Population of the Study

The population of the study will consist of seven thousand, two hundred and fifty seven (7,257) Senior Secondary School SS2 students in public secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial District of Delta State. This comprises of 140 males and 100 females. The SS2 students will be used for the study because they had already been assigned to specific disciplines and will also be available for use at any time because they will not be preparing for any external examinations.

Sample and Sampling Technique.

The sample size of two hundred and forty (240) SS2 chemistry students, comprising (140) males and (100) females participated in the study. The purposive sampling technique was carried out due to the fact that some schools do not have SS2 classes and some urban schools have larger number of students in their classes. Four (4) schools were selected out of the one hundred and ninety three (193) public secondary schools in Delta central senatorial district: two (2) from the rural area and two (2) from urban area. Two (2) non-randomized intact classes were used in each of the four schools to carry out the study.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument for data collection was a self-structured test named “Chemistry Performance Test” (CPT) and it will be used in the control and experimental groups. The Instrument will be prepared based on the content of instruction and consisted of a 20-item multiple-choice question each with four answer options A-D with only one correct answer choice to test the students’ knowledge on the topic. The Chemistry Performance Test (CPT) will be derived from the topic “Electrolysis and Redox reactions”. This topic will be taught using peer instructional strategy for experimental group and discussion method for control group. Instructional package will be given to the four (4) research assistants.

Validity of the Instrument

The instrument will be validated by an expert in measurement and evaluation from the Delta state University, Abraka and two other experts from the same University. The suggestions with regards to the scope, comprehensive, face and logical validity would be used to draw the final instruments. The items on the instrument will be checked to ascertain that the content measured were in accordance with the attributes to be evaluated. According to the American Educational Research Association (AERA), the American Psychological Association (APA), and the National Council on Measurement in Education (NCME) (2014), validity evidence is divided into content validity, construct validity, and criterion validity. Content validity is one of the conditions for the other validities. Content validity can be defined as how representative the items or tests are to measure the behaviour studied (Cohen & Swerdlik, 2018; Slaney, 2017).

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instruments will be determined by test-retest method. In this method, 20 copies of the questionnaire will be administered to 20 respondents outside the sample schools in Delta State who are not part of the sample for the study. After two weeks, the same instrument will be re-administered to the same people. The two sets of scores will be correlated using Person Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and a reliability coefficient of 0.83 was obtained.

Method of Data Collection

The researcher will visit the sampled schools during the first week to give an overview of the study to obtain permission from the principals of the participating schools. Following that, the control group and the experimental group's entire students’ body will be given the pre-test. In every school, the students will be divided into two groups during the second week: the experimental groups and the control groups. The experimental group will be introduced to peer tutoring while the control group would be introduced to the discussion approach and first lesson.

Research assistants will be the permanent chemistry teachers at the schools that would be sampled. The teachers would receive a briefing before the study's instructional phase begin. While the researcher would teach the experimental class, the school teachers would teach the control group. Subsequently, the researcher will select and direct an exceptionally talented student from the experimental group to assume the role of a peer-tutor following their acquisition of the ideas from their classmates.

Method of Data Analysis

The research questions will be answered using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses would be tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. The Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23 would be used for the analysis. A standard reference mean of 2.5 will be adopted for the purpose of determining the impact of peer instructional strategy on students’ academic performance in chemistry.

Research Procedure

Two (2) weeks will be for the training of the research assistants in the concept of peer instructional strategy. One (1) week will be for post-test for all groups. Eight (8) weeks will be dedicated to the experimental teaching sessions. One (1) week will be used for post-test for all groups. The researcher and the research assistants will be administering the CPT that will be drawn from the chemistry curriculum, and an instructional package will be designed by the researcher.

Expected Outcomes

1. The result of this study is expected to establish whether peer tutoring instructional strategy has a significant influence on the mean academic performance scores of students in chemistry in Senior Secondary Schools.
2. The result of this study is expected to establish whether peer tutoring instructional strategy has significant influence on the mean scores of students' academic performance in chemistry studies in Senior Secondary Schools.
3. The result of this study is expected to establish whether peer tutoring instructional strategy has significant influence on the mean academic performance scores of male and female students in chemistry in Senior Secondary Schools.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This section dealt with the presentation of results according to research questions and research hypotheses and discussion of findings.

Research Question 1: *What is the academic performance mean scores of students taught chemistry by the use of peer instructional strategy and those taught with discussion method?*

Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the academic performance mean scores of students taught chemistry by the use of peer instructional strategy and those taught by the use of discussion method.

Table 1: Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) of students' academic performance mean scores in chemistry of those taught by the use of peer instructional strategy and those taught by the use of discussion method.

Source	Type III sum of squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	15602.515	2	7801.257	78.330	.000
Intercept	247608.885	1	247608.885	248.618	.000
Pretest	.015	1	.015	.000	.990
Method	14550.996	1	14550.996	146.103	.000
Error	3684.996	117	99.54		
Total	251850.000	120			
Corrected Total	19287.500	119			

A.R squared= .809 (Adjusted R Square=.799)

Table 1 result was used to determine whether the students' academic performance scores in chemistry significantly differ between that of those taught by using peer instructional strategy and those taught by the use of discussion method. Table 4.7 shows that on F-ratio of 146.10 with associated probability value of .00 were obtained. The probability value of .00 was compared with .05 and it was found to be significant as .00 was less than .05 ($P < .05$). The hypothesis one, H₀₁ was therefore rejected and inference drawn that, there is significant difference between the academic achievement mean scores of students taught chemistry by the use of collaborative peer instructional strategy and those taught by the use of discussion method.

Research Question 2: *What is the difference in the academic performance mean score of the urban and rural students taught chemistry by the use peer instructional strategy.*

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation scores of urban and rural.

Teaching Method	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain	Main Diff
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD		
Urban Sch.	30	31.00	9.67	85.00	15.04	54	
Rural Sch.	30	26.50	9.61	56.50	9.78	30	24
Total	60						

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 2 shows that in the pre-test the urban school had a mean score of 31.00 with standard deviation of 9.67 while in the post-test had a mean score of 85.00 with standard deviation of 15.00 and a mean gain of 54 was obtained. Also, in the pre-test, the rural school had a mean score of 26.50 with standard deviation of 9.61 whereas in the post-test had a mean score of 56.50 with standard deviation of 9.78 and a mean gain of 30 was obtained. A mean difference of 24 was obtained on favour of the urban school.

Hypothesis 3

H0₄: There is no significant difference in the academic performance mean scores of Urban and Rural Students taught Chemistry using Collaborative Peer Instructional Strategy in Delta State.

Research Question 3: *What is the difference in the academic performance mean scores of the male and female students taught chemistry using instructional strategy and discussion method?*

Table 4: Mean and standard deviation scores of male and female students taught chemistry by the use of collaborative peer instructional strategy.

Gender	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
Male	35	28.00	9.94	86.57	187	58.57
Female	25	27.60	9.26	88.00	19.5	60.40
Mean Diff						1.83

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 4 shows that the males in the pretest group had a mean score of 28.00 with standard deviation of 9.94. While in the posttest group the males had a mean score of 86.57 with standard deviation of 18.7. Also, in the pretest group the females had a mean score of 27.60 with standard deviation score of 9.26 whereas in the posttest group they had a mean score of 88.00 with standard deviation score of 19.5. The males had a mean gain of 58.57 while the females had a mean gain of 60.40. A mean difference of 1.83 was obtained in the favour of the females that one exposed to collaborative peer instructional strategy.

Table 4: Analysis of covariance (ANOVA) of significance difference in the academic performance mean score of male and female students.

Source	Type III sum of squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	573.702 ^a	2	286.851	.792	.458
Intercept	54756.430	1	54756.430	151.183	.000
Pretest	543.940	1	543.940	1.502	.225
Gender	24.540	1	24.540	.068	.767
Error	20644.631	57	362.187		
Total	47100.000	60			
Corrected Total	21218.333	59			

a. R Squared=.027 (Adjusted R Squared=.007)

The result of table 4.9 was used to determine whether there is significant difference in the mean academic performance difference of the male and female students taught chemistry using collaborative peer

instructional strategy. Table 4.9 shows that an F-ratio of .068 with probability value of .79 were obtained. The probability value of .79 was compared with .05 and it was formed to be greater than .05 ($P > .057$). Hence the null hypothesis three, H_{O3} was accepted and inference drawn that, there is no significant difference in the academic performance mean score of the male and female students taught chemistry by the use of collaborative peer instructional strategy.

Summary of Findings

1. In Table 4.1 the experimental group had a mean gain of 65.00 while the control had a mean gain of 30.75. A mean difference of 34.25 was obtained in favour of experimental group (Collaborative peer instructional strategy). Further, use of analysis of covariance showed that, there was significant difference in the academic performance mean scores of those taught by collaborative peer instructional strategy and those taught by the use of discussion method $P < .05$.
2. In table 4.2, the mean difference observed was 27.75 in favour of the experimental group (think-pair-share). Furthermore, use of analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) in table 4.8 showed that, there was significant difference, $P < .05$ between Think-pair-share peer instructional strategy and discussion method.
3. The result in table 4.3 showed a mean difference of 15.00 in favour of experimental group (Male and Female). A further analysis by the use of analysis of variance (ANCOVA) showed that, there was significant difference between the experimental group(male) mean scores and that of control group (female) in table 4.9, $P < .05$.
4. In table 4.4, the mean difference of 24 was obtained in favour of urban schools. A further analysis by the use of analysis of variance in table 4.10 showed that, there was significant difference on the main scores of urban schools and rural schools, $P < .05$.
5. The result of table 4.5 yields a mean difference of 32.55 in favour of the experimental group (males). And a further analysis by the use of analysis of variance (ANCOVA) shows that, there was significant difference in the mean scores of the experimental group and that of control group, $P < .05$.
6. In table 4.6 a mean difference of 6.00 was obtained in favour of the females. Further analysis by the use of analysis of variance shows that, there was no significant difference in the mean scores of males and females taught chemistry by the use of Think-pair-share peer instructional strategy, $P > .05$.

4.3 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The following discussion of the data analysis results is based on the study questions and related hypotheses.

Performance of Students taught chemistry using Collaborative peer instructional Strategy and those taught using Discussion Method

The results of study question 1 hypothesis 1 in Tables 4.1 and 4.7 respectively, demonstrated the substantial impact that the Collaborative peer instructional strategy technique had on secondary school chemistry students' academic achievement. This may be the case because chemistry is a subject that requires cooperative, competitive, brainstorming teaching strategies such as the peer assisted learning strategy—in terms of collaborative strategy, rather than just any of the traditional teaching methods (lecture, demonstration, and inquiry, etc.). The finding is in collaboration with Olalekan (2016), who found that when students receive essential peer support, they are more likely to achieve and exceed their capabilities, focus more on their studies, and perform well in academic tasks at school than their counterparts.

Performance of Urban and Rural Students taught chemistry using Peer collaborative Learning Strategy and discussion method

The results of research question 4 and hypothesis 4, which are displayed in tables 4.4 and 4.10, respectively, demonstrated that there was a significant difference between the academic performance of secondary school students from urban and rural areas who were taught chemistry using collaborative strategy. The urban secondary school students in the experimental group fared better than the rural

students. This is because peer-assistant learning strategies give students the freedom to express themselves freely because they are learning and teaching themselves.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study's conclusions led to the following recommendations:

1. Teachers should make more use of collaborative instructional strategy to raise the academic performance level.
2. Discussion instructional strategy should be used while teaching students chemistry concepts.
3. Males and females should be taught using either collaborative or think-pair-share peer instructional strategy.

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